

Table 2. Yield data of the Mahsuri-derived varieties under multilocational testing. Assam, India, 1989-91.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)								
	Titabar ^a	North Lakhimpur ^a	Pambari ^b	Tinsukia ^b	Kalachand ^b	Mahakal ^b	North Lakhimpur ^b	Nowgaon ^b	
Kushal	5.8	4.3	5.8	3.6	6.1	4.5	2.5	5.5	6.3
Maniram	4.2	4.4	5.4	3.6	5.5	4.9	3.1	4.7	6.0
Bahadur	4.2	4.5	-	3.3	6.1	4.5	3.3	6.5	5.3
Ranjit	4.2	-	5.3	3.2	4.2	4.4	3.9	5.8	6.1
Mahsuri (check)	3.2	4.2	4.0	-	2.5	-	2.3	4.0	4.0

^aRARS. ^bField trial station. All tests were conducted in 1991 except those in Titabar, which were in 1989 and 1990.

On-farm evaluation of rice cultivars for spring season in the lower hills of Chitwan, Nepal

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Most farmers in the village of Kholaghari and a few in the village of Daletar in Chitwan, Nepal, have farmer-managed irrigation systems and can grow irrigated transplanted rice in the spring before the main season rice crop. Many farmers, however, keep their lands fallow or grow maize in the spring because suitable rice cultivars are not available and they are unsure whether an early rice could be grown successfully.

We evaluated six promising rice cultivars in irrigated bunded terraces of seven farmers' fields (six in Kholaghari and one in Daletar) from Mar to Jul 1992. Soil was sandy loam or loam, with 5.1-7.6 N, 0.03-0.06 kg available P/ha, and 10-58 kg available K/ha. Each farmer's field served as one replication; plots were 60 m². Two to three seedlings/hill were transplanted at the spacing used by the farmers. Fertilizers were applied at 60:8.8:16.6 kg NPK/ha. Half of the N and all of the P and K were applied as basal; the remaining N was topdressed at the grain-filling stage. The participant farmers completely managed the trials.

We found significant differences among rice cultivars for most characters. Chaite-2 and Ghaiya-2 yielded the most among cultivars (Table 1).

We requested the farmers to assemble to evaluate the trials after harvest. A matrix ranking was done on cultivar

Table 1. Mean grain yield and other agronomic characters^a of 6 early rice cultivars grown in 7 farmers' fields. Chitwan, Nepal, Mar-Jul 1992.

Cultivar	Productive tillers/m ² (no.)	Nonproductive tillers/m ² (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Days to heading (no.)	Days to maturity (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Chaite-2	75 ab	7 ab	115 a	66 a	97 a	4.8 ab
Chaite-4	73 ab	11 a	95 b	58 c	88 c	4.2 bc
Ghaiya-2	74 ab	8 ab	106 ab	62 b	93 b	5.2 a
Radha-2	58 b	6 b	95 b	53 d	84 d	4.2 bc
Radha-32	75 ab	7 ab	106 ab	63 b	97 a	4.1 bc
Farmers' variety ^b	84 a	8 ab	112 a	56 ab	98 a	3.9 c
CV (%)	21.2	48.2	13.1	3.6	2.9	15.7

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bDiffered among farmers. Two used Laxmi, while the others used CH45.

Table 2. Matrix ranking of early rice cultivars grown by participant farmers, Chitwan, Nepal, Mar-Jul 1992.

Attribute	Varieties					
	Chaite-2	Chaite-4	Ghaiya-2	Radha-2	Radha-32	Laxmi
Yield						
Grain	7	3	5	3	4	8
Straw	6	3	3	8	4	6
Tillering	7	4	5	3	4	7
Disease resistance	7	4	5	3	4	8
Insect resistance	7	3	5	3	4	8
Early maturity	4	6	5	7	4	4
Shattering	6	4	5	4	5	6
Threshing ease	4	6	5	7	4	4
Dormancy	7	3	5	4	4	7
Milling recovery	5	4	5	5	6	5
Grain weight	6	4	4	6	3	7
Cooking quality	6	5	5	4	4	6
Best variety:	Two farmers - Laxmi Rest of the farmers - Chaite-2					

attributes. Farmers were given 30 maize kernels and asked to allot them to show the relative differences among the cultivars for a particular attribute. After discussion, farmers agreed on how the maize kernels should be allotted. The same procedure was used for all attributes.

When asked which cultivar they would choose if they could only use one, two farmers chose Laxmi, while the rest chose Chaite-2 (Table 2). When asked which

cultivars they would plant next year, all of them chose Chaite-2 and Laxmi. The participant farmers reported that many other farmers visited their trials and asked for seeds of Laxmi and Chaite-2. We concluded that local farmers preferred these two cultivars.

Farmers considered Chaite-2 and Laxmi superior to the other cultivars, although we thought Chaite-2 and Ghaiya-2 were the outstanding cultivars. ■